

An Improved Markov Model for the Urban SOTM Channel

Tim Gillespie and Clark Robertson
Electrical and Computer Engineering Department
Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey, CA 93943-5121

Abstract— *In the time domain, the COTM channel is best modeled as a Markov generative process. The Baum-Welch parameter estimation algorithm is applied to empirical data collected in Boston, MA. The parameter estimation algorithm provides guidance for the development of a Markovian generative model to represent the ULMSC fade function in a larger time-based simulation. Three different continuous output transmission Markov models are presented and results are compared with discrete output Markov models. The continuous output models produce more accurate state durations, provide signal strength as a function of time and generally advance previous modeling efforts. The improved generative channel models also support the development of a larger time-based network simulation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

On-going advancements in telecommunications have raised the U.S. military's expectations regarding the quality, flexibility and robustness of future communication services. One area of increased expectation is in developing a capability to maintain high data rate, secure communications with mobile military units in any environment. This expectation can be seen in the Army's *Communications-On-The-Move* (COTM) concept and the Navy's *Sea Power 21 / FORCENet* concepts. In these concepts, the Army and Navy pursue an infrastructure that maintains high data rate connections with land vehicles, sea vessels, UAVs, and the individual dismounted soldier. The research presented in this paper is primarily focused on land vehicles communicating with geosynchronous satellites, which is sometimes referred to as *SATCOM-On-The-Move* (SOTM). In order to be mobile, jam-resistant and high data rate, these SOTM channels are expected to use highly directional antennas (e.g. parabolic). While the terms COTM and SOTM are relatively recent, the basic problem has traditionally been known in the academic literature as the Land Mobile Satellite Channel (LMSC) and before that, the Land Mobile Radio Channel (LMRC). In fact, the SOTM link discussed in this paper is a specific type of LMSC that relies on directional antennas for both ends of the physical interface.

Initial research into developing the SOTM capability has found the urban environment to be the most challenging due to the extreme depth and duration of signal fades caused by building blockage [10]. This paper is focused on improving the channel model for this environment. In this paper, we provide a brief history of the LMSC/SOTM channel models, summarize the empirical data used for this investigation and present results

for an improved model. It is important to note that while this paper has a limited focus on the development of an improved model for the urban SOTM channel, the improved model is not a means unto itself. Instead, the improved model is only the first step towards investigating performance enhancing solutions for a deployed system. Two specific improvements investigated by the authors include blockage circumvention and fade prediction schemes [12].

II. MODELING THE LMSC: HISTORY

The LMRC and LMSC have been under investigation for over 40 years and a rich body of research exists.[1,2,3] The majority of that research has been focused on modeling the channel with a probability density model. Initially these density models were relatively simple but not very accurate at reproducing the combined impacts of signal attenuation, shadowing and multi-path interference. In an effort to overcome this shortfall, later efforts explored linear combinations of simple density models or nested, conditional density models where input parameters were also stochastic functions. These more sophisticated methods produced mixture models that produced bi-modal or multi-modal outputs more closely aligned with empirical results. Within this body of research, it was frequently noted that the mobile's environment (i.e. rural, suburban, urban) was an extremely important factor in channel performance and that channel models were most accurate for a specific environment.

While the complex density models are more accurate than their predecessors, they still have an inherent drawback. This drawback is that they are limited to analyzing the long-term statistics of the channel (i.e. average fade duration, level crossing rate, etc.). These probability density models are not the best way to understand or model the short term activity in the channel because they treat the non-stationary channel as stationary and do not take into consideration channel memory. To address these short-comings and further improve LMSC modeling, some scientists have proposed the use of Markov models. [6,7,8,9] These authors still supported the basic concept of using different pdfs to model different environments (urban, suburban, rural, open), but instead of combining different pdfs into a single amalgam, they assigned a pdf to each state and transitioned between states using a hidden Markov model (HMM). [6,7,8,9] This idea is illustrated by Figure 1, where the state transition diagram is shown for a three-state Markov model. State S_1 is defined as an open environment without shadowing. States S_2 and S_3 are similarly defined as suburban and urban environments with incrementally more shadowing and multi-path. The

variables P_{ij} represent transition probabilities from state S_i to state S_j .

Figure 1. Markov model for LMSC [7].

As a mobile receiver moves it tends to stay within a specific environment for a relatively long period of time. While the receiver is in state S_1 , the LOS signal is not blocked and the channel can be modeled using a Ricean pdf. While the receiver is in state S_2 , the LOS signal is occasionally attenuated and scattered by trees or small buildings. So the best pdf for this situation may be Rayleigh with a log normal mean, as suggested by Loo [4]. An appropriate pdf is also assigned to the urban state S_3 . One possibility is Schodorf's suggestion that the urban environment is accurately represented by a mixture of three pdfs [10].

Figure 2. Short, medium and long-term variation of signal strength with time. Long-term (“very slow”) variation is modeled by state transitions shown in Figure 1 [7].

Figure 2 shows this model from a temporal perspective. The figure delineates between three orders of variation in the signal strength. The “fast” variations are usually attributed to multi-path fading. The “slow” variations are usually associated with specific shadowing events by foliage, terrain or buildings. The “very slow” variations are associated with changes in the environment.

The research presented in this paper narrows the focus to further investigate the urban state (S_3 above). As mentioned above, hidden Markov modeling is an important modeling approach for the general LMSC with states $S_1 - S_3$ representing

the rural, suburban and urban environments, respectively. As part of this research, we have also proposed another embedded HMM internal to the urban state. This embedded urban HMM provides an improved generative model of the urban shadowing phenomenon than achieved through a simple density model. The improved accuracy achieved with this approach will be discussed in Section V. An urban Markov channel model also provides a more accurate representation of real-world channel memory where neighboring time samples are not truly independent. This benefit makes Markov models better at producing short-term, time-sampled, outputs.

The basic idea of using an additional, embedded HMM within a specific environment state of a general LMSC HMM is not new. In [10], Schodorf attempts to model the SOTM LMSC in three different environments with a simple two-state Markov or Gilbert model. Schodorf investigated three different approaches to modeling the SOTM channel as a Markov chain. The first was a non-hidden, discrete, two-state Markov model. The second and third were both implementations of the Gilbert model. The difference between his second and third modeling attempt was the approach to computing model parameters. The second model was parameterized using only the average connection statistics found in the empirical data. While this version produced an excellent fit to the empirical connection statistics, it did not provide an acceptable fit to the fade statistics. The third and final attempt was parameterized jointly using both connection and fade statistics. Schodorf's results are summarized in Section V.

The research presented in this paper is focused on improving upon Schodorf's results at developing a model that matches empirical test results. The empirical data is discussed in the next section. This research assumes that the general LMSC channel is being modeled such that the different environments are represented as state changes in a macroscopic HMM [6,7,8,9]. The research then focuses on the state that represents the urban environment and inserts an additional continuous transmission hidden Markov process into the urban state. This research also assumes that the mobile node has a directional antenna as planned for the Army's COTM/SOTM concept. This is an important assumption because it prevents the channel from relying on multi-path signal power. For this situation, the LOS signal is considered the only input to the receiver.

III. EMPIRICAL DATA

As part of the overall effort to understand and model the COTM channel, investigators at Lincoln Laboratory built a hardware test platform and used it to collect empirical data in 2002. This test program had a broad set of goals including channel characterization, antenna pointing performance, and packet protocol performance in open, rural and urban environments [10]. The SOTM channel testing utilized an operational MILSTAR satellite to represent the satellite node of the channel. The mobile node was represented by a military vehicle equipped with a 12 in. directional antenna. Because the focus of this paper is limited to the urban communications channel, the discussion here is focused on the channel characterization (signal strength) subset of the urban data set

collected in Boston. The test data includes a 10 Hz measurement of the signal-to-noise ratio (Pr/No), and a 7 Hz measurement of the vehicle velocity. As an example, Figure 3 shows an excerpt of the signal strength from one data set. It is important to note that the signal strength data presented in Figure 3 has not been shifted to be relative to LOS.

Figure 3. Signal strength vs. time (relative to LOS).

As part of this investigation, we analyzed the data histogram as a pseudo-density function, computed and analyzed the state dwell times, and converted temporally dependent data into spatially dependent data. Each of these topics are discussed more below.

A. Histogram of Raw Data

An important method for analyzing the empirical data is the histogram, which can approximate the probability density function (pdf). Unlike the data presented in Figure 3, this signal strength data is presented in its original empirical form and is not shifted to be relative to LOS.

The largest histogram peak is centered near 75 dB and actually shows up as a double peak separated by about 3 dB. This double peak is expected and represents clear communication between the mobile vehicle and the satellite. The next largest feature occurs around 40-45 dB. This peak accounts for time steps where the receiver is experiencing a deep fade. It is important to note that the region between these two peaks, which extends from approximately 50-65 dB, shows a low probability of receiving partial signal fade more associated with foliage. As Schodorf notes, the empirical data is influenced by the design of the hardware test bed and does not reflect theoretical expectations [10]. The front end of the mobile test bed includes a hard-limiter that modifies the true density function by saturating and truncating the highest signal powers. One side effect of this hard-limiting front end are the two neighboring peaks near 74 and 76 dB. At the other end of the histogram, the test bed is not able to detect signal power below its noise floor, which is approximately 35 dB. This prevents the histogram from tapering off smoothly below 35 dB.

Figure 4. Histogram of raw empirical data.

B. Interarrival or Dwell Times

Another important parameter of the fade process is the time between state transitions. We will refer to this parameter as *dwell* time [10]; some authors also refer to it as *interarrival time* (time between events) [11]. Using Kendall's notation for a simple M/M/1 queue, we model the interarrival time as an exponential random variable where the probability of an event after k time steps is

$$\Pr(n = k) = \frac{e^{-k}}{k}. \quad (0.1)$$

For a Markov model with two states, this relationship can be modified to reflect the actual transition probabilities of the problem. The probability of being in state i for k time steps is

$$\Pr(s_t \dots s_{t+k} = i) = a_{ii}^k (1 - a_{ii}). \quad (0.2)$$

For this specific problem, we have two defined states: connection and fade. It is important to investigate the duration statistics of these two states separately. Figures 5 and 6 show the complementary CDF for each state duration. Summary statistics for the original temporal data set are also shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary statistics for basic data set.

(all data in seconds)	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Maximum
Connection durations	5.39	11.05	99.1
Fade durations	1.68	2.78	30.9

The complementary CDFs are shown on a logarithmic scale for easy comparison to exponential or geometric processes, which would appear linear. While the empirical dwell times aren't perfectly linear, they do appear to be roughly

approximated as linear. This is another indication that the urban SOTM channel fade process can be approximated as Markovian.

Figure 5. CDF of connection duration (original, temporal data).

Figure 6. CDF of fade duration (original, temporal data).

C. Conversion from Time Sampling to Spatial Sampling

As mentioned earlier, both the signal strength and velocity data were originally collected and presented as functions of time, $s(t)$ and $v(t)$. The data analysis already presented was completed in the time domain. But it is also important to analyze the data from the spatial perspective.

In the time domain, the signal vector represents a specific case of a mobile moving through an urban environment using a specific speed profile. Buildings are fixed spatially, and analyzing the problem from this perspective should provide insights regarding average building width and average gap width in meters. After converting the empirical data to the spatial domain, we can also generate additional signal strength vectors in the time domain by applying a different mobile velocity pattern.

The core of the conversion algorithm is a simple Riemann Sum. We can estimate the distance traveled during a sample period, by assuming that the velocity is constant over that sample period. By collecting these small distances in a running total, we are performing a simple integration using the Riemann Sum approach. The result of this simple algorithm is distance traveled (or vehicle location) versus time. After matching the signal strength and vehicle location in time, we can drop the relationship with time and use the direct comparison of signal strength as a function of distance traveled.

The summary statistics are shown in Table 2 and Figures 7 through 9 for direct comparison with the temporal data. Table 2 shows a mean fade duration of 16 meters (~ 52 feet), which seems to be a reasonable width for an average building. Of course, this average is not based only on buildings and is skewed smaller by

the inclusion of very narrow scatter sources like light poles and street signs. It is also interesting to note a shift in the ratio of connection statistics to fade statistics. While the mean and maximum connection durations are 3.2 times longer than the mean and maximum fade durations in time, the equivalent ratio is only 2.2 in distance. This odd relationship implies that, on average, the vehicle velocity is lower during connections than fades. Perhaps this is an impact of city traffic signals, where the vehicle generally has clear access to the satellite while sitting still for a red light. Clearly, the velocity profile of the mobile has a substantial impact on the channel performance.

The histogram in Figure 7 is surprisingly similar to that computed for the temporal data. It clearly shows the strong impact and bimodal nature of the connection/fade process. Like their temporal counterparts, the complementary CDFs plotted in Figures 8 and 9 are roughly approximated as linear, which reflects a nearly geometric distribution of dwell times.

Table 2. Summary statistics for spatial data set.

(all data in meters)	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Maximum
Connection durations	36.4	62.3	379.50
Fade durations	16.0	26.2	188.25

Figure 7. Histogram, spatial data (signal power vs. distance traveled).

Figure 8. CDF of connection duration (spatial data).

Figure 9. CDF of fade duration (spatial data).

IV. DEVELOPING A MODEL

In [10] Schodorf proposed modeling the urban SOTM channel with simple two-state generative models, including both non-hidden Markov and Gilbert models. These models are simple enough that they do not require an Expectation-Maximization algorithm like Baum-Welch, as model parameters can be directly estimated from the empirical data set. Schodorf’s results are summarized in Section V where it can be seen that additional improvements appear to be possible. In an effort to achieve those additional improvements, we increase model complexity by assuming continuous output transmission functions for the generative model.

We investigated three additional hidden Markov models, each with a continuous density function for the output transmission. In the first approach, we assumed a single Gaussian distribution for the output of each state. The second approach models each state as a weighted mixture of five Gaussians. The additional complexity of this approach allows the algorithm to resolve a more complex transmission function. The final approach converts the histograms presented earlier in this paper into continuous pdfs by implementing a piecewise polynomial.

A. Transmission Function: Gaussian or Gaussian Mixture

The smallest increase in complexity that still provides a continuous probabilistic output transmission function is a single Gaussian output function. The unknown parameters are the transition probabilities and the mean and variance for the Gaussian pdf associated with each state (i.e., a_{00} , a_{11} , μ_0 , μ_1 , σ_0^2 , σ_1^2). This makes a total of six unknown parameters to be estimated, which is double the three necessary for a Gilbert model (i.e., a_{00} , a_{11} , h).

While a single Gaussian transmission pdf may provide a more accurate representation of the signal strength than the Bernoulli function used by Schodorf, it is still a poor match to the histograms shown in Figures 4 and 7. A mixture of multiple Gaussians can often be an increasingly accurate replacement for a non-Gaussian stochastic process. The first and only attempt at this approach involved a five Gaussian mixture for each state. The 32 unknown parameters include two transition probabilities, the mean and variance for ten Gaussian distributions and ten weighting factors. As shown in the results, the fourth and fifth

mixture components were minor contributors and an increase in the mixture count was not necessary.

B. Transmission Function: Hermite Interpolant

While a mixture of weighted Gaussian functions provides a significant amount of flexibility in representing a complex stochastic process, it may not be as accurate as using the actual data itself. One idea for achieving these improvements was to model the process output with a more accurate probability density function. Thus, we investigated deriving an analytical expression for the histogram (as shown in Figures 4 and 7) using a hermite interpolant piecewise polynomial.

The first step towards completing this approach is to split the histogram into two distinct, but continuous pdfs, each representing a state. The logical separation point between the two states is the low point between the histogram two peaks. A windowed average of the histogram showed this general low point to be near 59 dB. Next, the histogram value at 59 dB was shared equally with both pdfs. Then a straight line was formed from that center point to the distant edge of the histogram. Each straight line was sloped to gently decrease until reaching zero at the edge of the pdf.

One benefit of this approach is the simplification of the Baum-Welch parameter estimation. With this piecewise polynomial approach, the pdf is assumed to be known and is no longer updated iteratively. The simplification provides a significant reduction in mathematical operations.

V. PARAMETER ESTIMATION RESULTS

A. Schodorf’s Results

Recall from Section II that Schodorf tried three different modeling approaches. Schodorf applied each of these three modeling approaches to open, rural, and urban environments. He also ran the models with both a -3 dB connection/fade threshold and a -10 dB connection/fade threshold where the threshold is relative to LOS. We will only present Schodorf’s model parameters for the urban environment with a -10 dB threshold because this is the closest match for comparison to the work presented in this paper. [10]

Table 3. Parameter estimation results from Schodorf [10].

	a_{00} (connection) ¹	a_{11} (fade) ¹	π_{fade} ¹
Markov (observable)	0.9726	0.9465	0.34
Gilbert	0.9748	0.9151	0.04
Gilbert (jointly opt.)	0.9959	0.9264	0.05

¹ Note: We can find the remainder of parameters by ($a_{01} = 1 - a_{00}$), ($a_{10} = 1 - a_{11}$), and ($\pi_{\text{connection}} = 1 - \pi_{\text{fade}}$)

Table 3 shows the state transition and steady state probabilities π estimated by each approach. Schodorf also solves for other parameters like the Bernoulli distribution parameter h but they are not repeated here since they are not valuable for comparison.

While the Gilbert model provides improved accuracy for the open and rural environments, it does not do so for the urban environment. In [10], Schodorf selects the simple Markov model as the best overall solution for the urban SOTM channel. The connection-based Gilbert model has the best fit for connection dwell time statistics, but otherwise, both Gilbert models significantly underestimate the fade statistics (a_{11} , π_{fade}). When compared to the dwell intervals seen in the empirical data, the Markov parameters shown above appear to be underestimated. Schodorf goes on to note that short connection durations are substantially underestimated and long connection durations are overestimated. He also notes an opposite skew of overestimating short fades and underestimating long fades.

B. Mixed-Gaussian Results

In an effort to find a better approach to converting empirical data into an accurate fade model, we replaced Schodorf's discrete-output transmission functions with continuous output transmission functions. This increases the complexity of solving for model parameters and requires the application of parameter estimation techniques, like Expectation-Maximization. The process was repeated for the original temporal data and the post-processed spatial data (see Section III). A common implementation involves assuming the transmission pdfs are a weighted mixture of individual Gaussian pdfs. In this implementation, the BWA estimates the transition probabilities of the Hidden Markovian process and the mean, variance and weighting coefficients of the combined Gaussian pdfs that represent each state. We investigated the simplest version with a single Gaussian pdf representing each state and also a more complex implementation where each state was represented by a mixture of five Gaussian pdfs. Each approach was attempted numerous times, each with a different random initial guess. The initial guess was originally expected to have only a small impact on results. Results did not completely conform to this expectation. Instead, some iterations did not converge within the maximum allowed number of iterations.

The results for a single Gaussian transmission function are shown in Table 4. The table shows numerical results for transition probabilities (a_{ii}) and transmission function parameters (μ_i , σ_i^2). Shown after each parameter is the approximate variance computed from ten independent attempts. These variances are extremely tight and reflect an insensitivity to the range of initial guesses explored.

The parameter estimation process was repeated for both temporal and spatial data sets discussed earlier in Section III. The spatial data (signal strength vs. meters traveled) is the appropriate data set for comparison with Schodorf's results since he used spatial data to generate the results shown in Table 3. In general it appears that this approach may slightly overestimate the fade and connection statistics but appears to be more accurate than the Gilbert model used by Schodorf.

Table 4. BWA results for a Gaussian transmission function (mean, variance for 10 attempts)

	Original Data (temporal)	Spatial Data
a_{00}	$0.9630, 10^{-15}$	$0.9876, 10^{-15}$
a_{11}	$0.9820, 10^{-16}$	$0.9923, 10^{-17}$
State 1: Mean	$74.694, 10^{-12}$	$74.711, 10^{-11}$
State 1: Variance	$1.4042, 10^{-11}$	$0.9679, 10^{-10}$
State 0: Mean	$49.065, 10^{-10}$	$46.925, 10^{-9}$
State 0: Variance	$179.91, 10^{-8}$	$134.30, 10^{-6}$

A more advanced approach to representing complicated transmission functions is to model them as a weighted mixture of multiple Gaussian functions. The BWA results for a weighted mixture of five Gaussian functions are shown in Tables 5 through 7 and Figures 10 through 12. Tables 5 and 6 and Figure 9 show the results of a single parameter estimation. Tables 5 and 6 show the five individual mixture component pdf parameters separately along with their weighting coefficients. In State 1 (connection), the weighting coefficients for pdfs 4 and 5 are so small as to make those mixture components nearly negligible. Figure 10 presents the final output transmission functions $b_1(O_i)$ and $b_2(O_i)$, which are computed by combining the mixture component pdfs in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5. Estimated model parameters for transmission functions (State 1).

Gaussian pdfs	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
Mean	75.52	74.72	73.67	71.30	67.94
Variance	0.67	1.29	0.14	3.79	6.34
Mixture weight	0.415	0.181	0.301	0.028	0.075

Table 6. Estimated model parameters for transmission functions (State 0).

Gaussian pdfs	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5
Mean	55.04	42.80	38.03	31.70	19.74
Variance	62.25	13.67	25.90	4.65	0.010
Mixture weight	0.344	0.327	0.275	0.006	0.047

Figure 10. BWA estimated mixture of five Gaussian pdfs each to represent States 0 and 1; each mixture combined to form a single pdf.

The performance of the BWA varied noticeably with initial guess as shown in Figure 11. Figure 11 shows the transmission pdfs estimated by the algorithm for five independent attempts; each limited to 200 iterations of the BWA. For State 1, attempts 1 and 5 resolved only one peak in the transmission function, while the remaining attempts resolved two peaks. Please note that the plot for attempt 1 is difficult to see because it is hidden behind attempt 5. For State 0, attempts 1, 3 and 5 resolved a distinct and heavily weighted spike in the pdf near 30 dB of signal strength. Attempts 1 and 5 certainly stand out as generally being of lower accuracy. Appropriately, these two attempts also had the lowest BWA likelihoods. Attempt #3 did not converge within the allowed number of iterations. Other attempts (not shown) were similar to the examples presented. The majority of attempts resolved two peaks in the State 1 (connection) pdf and did not resolve the sharp spike in the State 0 (fade) pdf.

Figure 11. Output transmission pdfs for five parameter estimation attempts using the original data set. (a) State 1 (connection), (b) State 0 (fade).

Figure 12. Output transmission pdfs for five parameter estimation attempts using the spatial data set. (a) State 1 (connection), (b) State 0 (fade).

This process was repeated with the spatial data set. The results for transition probability are summarized in Table 7. Figure 12 is similar to Figure 11, except that it is based on the spatial data set. After 250 iterations, two of the five attempts (1 and 4) were still resolving on a single peak. These two attempts had the lowest likelihoods.

By comparing the results in Table 7 to those in Table 4, we can see that the increased number of Gaussian pdfs used to represent the intra-state emission process unanimously increases the estimates for transition probability a_{ij} .

Table 7. BWA results: Gaussian mixture transition probabilities (mean, variance of 10 trials).

	a_{00}	a_{11}
Original Data	0.9657, 3E-6	0.9867, 2E-6
Spatial Data	0.9884, 3E-8	0.9935, 5E-8

C. Specific Discussion of Piecewise Polynomial Results

While the results from modeling the output of each state as a mixture of Gaussian random variables were promising, additional improvements seemed possible with a more accurate output transmission function. For the third and final approach, the weighted Gaussian mixtures presented in the last section were replaced with hermite interpolant-based, continuous pdfs.

As noted above, the number of unknown variables drops significantly with this approach because the output transmission pdfs no longer have parameters to be estimated. The only remaining parameters left for the Baum-Welch algorithm to estimate were the model's transition probabilities a_{ij} . The parameter estimations for a_{ij} are shown in Table 9. These transition probability results are uniformly higher than the interarrival times found in the empirical data. Due to poor accuracy, this approach was not pursued to completion and was only applied to the original, temporal data.

D. Summary of Parameter Estimation Results

Sections A. through C. presented the parameter estimation results achieved for each of the approaches discussed. These include the observable Markov model and Gilbert model implemented by Schodorf as well as the continuous transmission functions implemented as part of this research (i.e., Gaussian and Hermite Interpolant). The next step is to compare the relative performance of the different approaches and determine which approach is the most accurate. For a Markovian process, the transition probabilities are directly related the mean state dwell intervals:

$$E[t_{dwell}] = \frac{1}{a_{ij}} = \frac{1}{1 - a_{ii}}. \quad (0.3)$$

Based on the dwell interval statistics presented in Tables 1 and 2, we can directly estimate the transition probabilities as

shown in Tables 8 and 9. These direct estimates will provide a measuring stick with which to compare the other methods.

To compare the different continuous transmission HMMs with Schodorf's attempts, we need to analyze the results based on spatial data because that is the data Schodorf used. The parameter estimation results of the spatial data are summarized in Table 8. The best match is achieved with the mixed Gaussian transmission functions, indicated by the red ovals. The mixed Gaussian HMM provides a mean connection of 38.5 meters and a mean fade of 21.5 meters. These are both slightly longer than experienced by the empirical testing. The second best match is provided by the single Gaussian transmission functions; but the single Gaussian approach produces mean dwell intervals that are slightly smaller than found in testing. The observable Markov model and Gilbert model do not provide nearly as good of a match with respect to producing mean dwell intervals.

Table 8. Comparison of parameter estimation results for spatial data

Original data:	a_{11} (connection)	a_{00} (fade)
Direct estimate	0.9931	0.9844
Schodorf Markov	0.9726	0.9465
Schodorf Gilbert	0.9959	0.9264
Single Gaussian	0.9923	0.9876
Gaussian mixture	0.9935	0.9884

Table 9. Comparison of parameter estimation results for temporal data

Original data:	a_{11} (connection)	a_{00} (fade)
Direct estimate	0.9814	0.9405
Single Gaussian	0.9820	0.9630
Mixed Gaussian	0.9867	0.9657
Hermite interpolant	0.9906	0.9713

Table 9 provides a condensed comparison of the BWA results for the original (temporal) data set. In almost all cases the parameter estimation has overestimated the state durations, especially with respect to the fade state. The hermite interpolant approach consistently produces the largest estimates of transition probability regardless of state or dataset. These large transition probability estimates provide abnormally long fade and connection dwell intervals that are not reflected in the test data. Again, the two Gaussian-based approaches are closer to matching expectations and in some cases produce mean connection dwell intervals within a few seconds of the test data results.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present an improved urban COTM/SOTM channel model. The mixed-Gaussian continuous transmission hidden Markov model is superior to prior attempts in two ways. The first is the increased accuracy in matching dwell interval statistics. The second improvement over previous models is the model's ability to produce a time sequence of signal strength that accurately matches the empirical training data. This is a direct benefit of the model being a continuous transmission HMM. This improved SOTM channel model is a valuable tool when

investigating channel performance and analyzing design solutions focused on improving channel performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. F. Ossana, "A Model for Mobile Radio Fading Due to Building Reflections: Theoretical and Experimental Fading Waveform Power Spectra," *Bell Syst. Tech. J.*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 2935-2971, Nov. 1964.
- [2] R. H. Clarke, "A Statistical Theory of Mobile-Radio Reception," *Bell Syst. Tech. J.*, vol. 47, pp. 957-1000, July-Aug. 1968.
- [3] H. Suzuki, "A Statistical Model for Urban Radio Propagation," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. COM-25, no. 7, pp. 673-680, July 1977.
- [4] Chun Loo, "A Statistical Model for a Land Mobile Satellite Link," *IEEE Trans. on Veh. Technol.*, vol. VT-34, no. 3, pp. 122-127, 1985.
- [5] E. Lutz, D. Cygan, M. Dippold, F. Dolainsky and W. Papke, "The Land Mobile Satellite Communication Channel – Recording, Statistics, and Channel Model," *IEEE Trans. on Veh. Technol.*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 375-386, May 1991.
- [6] B. Vucetic and J. Du, "Channel modeling and simulation in satellite mobile communication systems," *IEEE J. Select. Areas Comm.*, pp. 1209-1218, Oct 1992.
- [7] Fernando Perez Fontan, Maryan Vazquez-Castro, Cristina Enjamio Cabado, Jorge Pita Garcia, Erwin Kubista, "Statistical modeling of the LMS channel," *IEEE Trans. on Veh. Technol.*, pp. 1549-1567, Nov. 2001.
- [8] H. Wakana, "A Propagation Model for Land-Mobile Satellite Communication," presented at the 1991 North American Radio Science Meeting and IEEE/APS Symposium, The University of Western Ontario, London, Ontario, Canada, June 1991.
- [9] Fulvio Babich, and Giancarlo Lombardi, "A Markov Model for the Mobile Propagation Channel," *IEEE Trans. on Veh. Technol.*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 63-73, January 2000.
- [10] J. B. Schodorf, *EHF Satellite Communications on the Move: Experimental Results*, Technical Report 1087, Lincoln Laboratory MIT, Boston, MA, Aug 2003.
- [11] Donald Gross and Carl Harris, *Fundamentals of Queueing Theory*, 3rd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1998.
- [12] Tim Gillespie, "Modeling the Transformational Communications System Urban Land Mobile Sattelite Channel", Doctoral Dissertation, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, CA, Oct 2007.